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Multifunctional Thermally Responsive Hydrogels Integrating Silver Nanoparticles and Herbal Medicines for Infected Wound Healing

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Wounds

Wound types

- **Any defect or damage in the tissues**
 - Acute wounds: surgical, traumatic injuries
 - Chronic wounds : pathophysiological conditions
(e.g. constant infection, diabetes)

Worldwide share of wound prevalence

Source: MedMarket Diligence, LLC

Incision

Laceration

Puncture

Burn

Amputation

Infected wound

Infected wound

Diabetic ulcer

Biological process for wound healing

Inflammation

- Phagocytizing
- cytokine/growth factor

Proliferation

- Formation of granulation tissue
- Angiogenesis
- Reepithelialization

Maturation

- Wound contraction
- Scar maturation

Wound treatment

Current approaches

Commercial wound care products

- Sutures, staples, sealants, hemostatic materials, adhesive glues
- Bandages, hydrocolloids, hydrogels, Forms
- Growth factors (EGF, FGF, *etc.*)
- Ointments

Limitations

- Preformed types
- Hard to load therapeutic agents
- Secondary infections
- Insufficient wound-healing

Current research for wound treatment

Therapeutic Vehicles

Fast curing time **Tissue adhesiveness** **Biocompatibility**

Therapeutic Agents

<p>Cell</p>	<p>Cells Embryonic stem cells IPS-cells MSCs EPCs Fibroblasts Keratinocytes</p>	<p>Protein drugs EGF, bFGF, PDGF VEGF, KGF, SDF-1,..</p> <p>Other drugs ROS (NO, H₂O₂)</p>	
<p>Protein</p>			

Bioactive materials facilitating wound-healing

Hydrogel materials

Hydrogels

- 3D hydrophilic polymer networks
- Absorb a large amount of water or biological fluids
- Mechanical and structural similarities to the native tissue
- Various biomedical applications
 - Wound dressings, transdermal drug delivery, therapeutic implants, implant coating materials, contact lens, *etc.*

J. A. Yang *et al. Prog. Polym. Sci.*, 2014, 39, 1973

Biomedical applications of hydrogel materials

Preformed hydrogels

In situ forming hydrogels

Contact lens

Transdermal drug delivery

Wound dressing

Implant coating materials

Tissue engineering scaffold

Hemostatic dressing

Wound closure

In situ forming hydrogels for wound treatment

Enhanced therapeutic efficacy and patient comfortability !

Easy application for large defects
(injectable or sprayable system)

Ability to fill irregular defects
(close contact to the surrounding tissue)

Easy loading of bioactive agents
(personalized treatment)

***In situ* forming hydrogels**

Local delivery of therapeutic agents
(minimally invasive implantation)

Thermo-responsive hydrogels

Advantages

- Tunability, simplicity and safety in *in vivo* situations
- Physical cross-linking responds to body temperature
- Injectability and easy loading of therapeutics

Design of multifunctional thermally responsive hydrogels

Motivation

To develop a multifunctional nanocomposite hydrogel by incorporating AgNPs and *Syzygium resinosum* leaf extract into a thermosensitive alginate-based hydrogel matrix for effectively promoting the wound healing of bacteria-infected tissues

Synthesis and characterization of thermosensitive ACP copolymer

Synthesis of ACP

¹H-NMR spectra

FT-IR:

- ~ 3420 cm⁻¹: O-H stretching
- ~2880 cm⁻¹: C-H (CH₂) stretching
- ~1720 cm⁻¹: N=C=O (isocyanate group)
- 1600-1700 cm⁻¹: amide I & II (C=O, N-H stretching)
- ~1060 cm⁻¹: C-O stretching

FT-IR

Synthesis and characterization of herbal-derived AgNPs

UV-Vis (effect of Ag⁺ conc.)

UV-Vis (effect of SR conc.)

FT-IR

XRD

TEM

DLS

Multifunctional thermoresponsive hydrogel

Preparation of ACP and ACP/SR@AgNPs hydrogel

Multifunctional thermoresponsive hydrogel

Rheological study of hydrogels (T_{gel} and elastic modulus)

Sol-gel transition temperature

Elastic modulus

Effect of incorporation of SR and AgNPs@SR into hydrogel network :

- (\downarrow) the T_{gel}
- (\uparrow) the gel stiffness (elastic modulus)

Multifunctional thermoresponsive hydrogel

Swelling behavior

Degradation rate

Effect of SR and AgNPs@SR on strengthening the hydrogel network, resulting to:

- (↓) the swelling ratio
- (↑) the degradation rate

Multifunctional thermoresponsive hydrogel

In vitro antibacterial activity (disc-diffusion method)

- ACP/SR and ACP/AgNPs@SR showed antibacterial activity, depending on the hydrogel volume.
- Higher inhibition effect against gram negative bacteria than gram positive bacteria

Multifunctional thermoresponsive hydrogel

Antioxidant activity

DPPH scavenging effect

Intracellular ROS inhibition

(Scale bar: 200 μ m)

The effect of SR and AgNPs incorporation:

- Increase the ability to scavenge DPPH free radicals
- Decrease intracellular ROS generation

→ facilitate the wound healing process

Multifunctional thermoresponsive hydrogel

In vitro cell toxicity (Live/dead assay)

Hemolysis ratio

- All hydrogels have good cytocompatibility to L929 cells, compared to that of free AgNPs@SR
- The hemolysis ratios were < 5% for all samples \rightarrow Non-hemolysis materials

In vivo wound healing efficacy of hydrogels

Schematic illustration of infected wound modeling and treatments

Obtained male mice
6–8 weeks old

Skin wound establishment
d = 10 mm

Wound coinfectd by
S. aureus and *P. aeruginosa*

Treatment
Day 0

Observation and photography
Day 4, 7*, 10, 14*

Sacrificing

* Blood samples were collected, and skin tissues were harvested from mice sacrificed on these days for hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining

Wound healing rate

Day 0 Day 4 Day 7 Day 10 Day 14

- The wound healing speed in all hydrogel groups was faster than that in the control group.
- ACP/AgNPs@SR hydrogel exhibited the best performance, attributed to the synergistic effect of SR and AgNPs

In vivo wound healing efficacy of hydrogels

H&E staining

ACP/AgNPs@SR hydrogels showed the best quality of healed skin, demonstrated by:

- Numerous new vessels, hair follicles or sebaceous glands
- Well-organized epidermis
- Highly bactericidal effect.

Bacterial colonies from the infected wound (14th d)

ACP/

ACP

ACP/SR

AgNPs@SR

(+) Control

(-) Control

Conclusions

- Multifunctional thermoresponsive hydrogels composed of alginate and herbal-derived AgNPs was developed as an advanced injectable materials for bacteria-infected wounds
- The integration of AgNPs@SR significantly enhanced the mechanical properties and imparted multifunctional biological activities, including antioxidant, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and cell-proliferative effects, while maintaining the injectability and thermo-responsive behavior of the hydrogel
- Importantly, the ACP/AgNPs@SR hydrogel effectively promoted wound healing in a full-thickness skin *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*-infected model
- We expect that the ACP/AgNPs@SR hydrogel holds significant potential as a advanced functional wound dressing for treating the infected skin wounds..

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